

The clinicopathological conference, (CPC) was organized by the MEU on 17 September 2023 aiming to utilize case based study method of teaching medicine. This was presented by the department of medicine. Here are the excerpts from the case.

AN UNUSUAL CASE OF MOVEMENT DISORDER

A 53-year-old Hindu, married female, housewife, graduate, resident of Jaipur presented with chief complaints of Involuntary Perioral Chewing movements, slurring of speech and abnormal finger movements for 10 years which further increased gradually. The movements of right hand were insidious in onset, constant, repetitive and purposeless chewing movements with lip smacking, intermittent opening and closing of jaw. It Initially started with episodes of short duration and gradually progressed to remain throughout the day. It disappeared in sleep, as observed by family members and were not altered by eye closure. It remained unaffected by voluntary movements but were affected by emotions/excitement. It was not affected on approaching an object. Slurred speech was insidious in onset, gradually progressive. Patient had Dysarthric type of speech with Normal loudness, Intonation and Low pitch.

There was No history of fall or loss of consciousness in past or weakness of upper and lower limbs and no facial deviation, no history of medications / seizure disorder/ palpitation/weight loss/ headache/vomiting/blurring of vision. Patient was a known case of Type-2 diabetes mellitus; on oral hypoglycemic agents (on glimepiride plus metformin) for last 6 years with good sugar controls. She had Hypertension and was on Anti-hypertensives for last 5 years (Telmisartan and Amlodipine). No history of surgery/hospitalization or any other chronic illness.

On examination, Patient was conscious, co-operative and well oriented to time, place and person, average built and nourished. Pulse rate 84/minute, regular in rhythm, normal volume, vessel wall not palpable, no radio-radial and radio-femoral delay, all peripheral pulses well felt. BP: 130/80 mmHg in right arm in supine position RR: 16/minute, thoraco-abdominal; Temperature: Afebrile by touch. Cranial Nerves were normal on examination.

The examination of the Motor System showed Muscle tone to be increased in right upper limb, rigidity was present (cog wheel type). Power: 5/5 in all four limbs. There was Involuntary movement present in fingers of right Hand-Arrhythmic, repetitive and purposeless, appear at rest, increased on excitement and getting emotional, not suppressible and not altered by eye closure, disappeared during sleep, however, there was no change on approaching an object. Examination of sensory system showed that all intact sensations. Cerebellar functions were intact. Gait showed mild slowness in getting up from sitting, freezing was noted on initiation with reduced step length and arm swing right > left with some distal choreiform movements

in right upper limb. **Cranium and spine and meninges** were within normal limit

She had mildly reduced facial expressions, with a staring look. Blink rate was reduced. Cog-wheel rigidity was more on the right side. Bradykinesia was present right > left. Mild perioral dyskinesia with lip smacking with jaw dyskinesia. Distal choreiform movements were also observed in the right hand. On **Slit lamp examination: No K-F ring was seen**

Clinical diagnosis: **Insidious onset gradually progressive oro-buccal dyskinesia with right distal choreiform movements with dysarthria with bradykinesia and cog-wheel rigidity s/o the extra-pyramidal tract involvement with mild cognition and psychiatric involvement. Clinical findings suggest a movement disorder associated with neurodegenerative changes of long duration with gradually progressive course.** Differential diagnosis included Likely a neurodegenerative disorder: Huntington's Disease/ Wilson's Disease/ NBIA/ Neuroacanthocytosis/ Atypical Parkinson's disease.

Routine blood and urine examination were within normal limits. MRI showed discrete and semi confluent old infarct with gliotic areas seen in centrumsemiovale, periventricular white matter and bilateral ganglia showed small vessel ischemic changes suggesting a possibility of pantothenate kinase associated neurodegeneration (PKAN).

DISCUSSION

NBIA (Neurodegeneration with Brain Iron Accumulation) are a heterogeneous group of genetic neurodegenerative disorders characterized by abnormalities in brain iron metabolism and with excess iron accumulation in the **globus pallidus** and to a lesser degree in the **substantia nigra** and sometimes adjacent areas. All of the NBIA disorders feature iron deposition in the globus pallidus but differ in the co-occurrence of other findings

Neurodegeneration with Brain Iron Accumulation: Genetic Types

Gene ¹	NBIA Genetic Type	MOI	% of all NBIA
<i>ATP13A2</i>	Kufor-Rakeb syndrome (OMIM 606693)	AR	Rare ²
<i>C19orf12</i>	Mitochondrial membrane protein-associated neurodegeneration (MPAN)	AR, AD ³	5%-10% ⁴
<i>COASY</i>	COASY protein-associated neurodegeneration ⁵ (CoPAN; OMIM 618266)	AR	Rare
<i>CP</i>	Aceruloplasminemia	AR	Rare
<i>DCAF17</i>	Woodhouse-Sakati syndrome	AR	Rare ⁶
<i>FA2H</i>	Fatty acid hydroxylase-associated neurodegeneration (FAHN)	AR	Rare ⁷
<i>FTL</i>	Neuroferritinopathy	AD	Rare
<i>PANK2</i>	Pantothenate kinase-associated neurodegeneration (PKAN)	AR	30%-35% ⁴
<i>PLA2G6</i>	PLA2G6-associated neurodegeneration (PLAN)	AR	10%-15% ⁴
<i>WDR45</i>	Beta-propeller protein-associated neurodegeneration (BPAN)	XL	40%-45% ⁴

PKAN (autosomal recessive) is a major form of NBIA accounting for approximately 50% of childhood NBIA with a prevalence of 1–3/million. The Clinical features include Extraparallel involvement -dystonia rigidity and parkinsonism – cranial onset with dysarthria later on involving

limbs; Pyramidal tract resulting in upper motor neuron signs of hypertonicity, hyperreflexia, and spasticity. Pigmentary retinopathy leading to visual impairment. Pattern of stepwise decline, with periods of relative clinical stability combined with episodic neurological deterioration, cognitive decline, and loss of motor skills. It is caused by mutations in the PANK2 gene on chromosome 20. Globally, the c.1561G>A missense mutation is the most common cause of PKAN.

Death is usually secondary to (i) cardiorespiratory complications and complications from malnutrition or status dystonicus.

Very few case reports have been from India, one being Parashari UC, Aga P et al did MR spectroscopy in pantothenate kinase-2 associated neurodegeneration. Panneer Devaraju, Bhuvanewari Arumugam et al reported an atypical PKAN in one family where 2 siblings, where first sibling symptoms at age of 32 in form of cervical dystonia, blepharospasm and cognitive decline. 2nd sibling had right hand dystonia, dysarthria, dysphagia psychiatric symptoms and cognitive decline. Both had "EYE OF TIGER" in MRI brain.

MANAGEMENT OF PKAN

Currently there are no disease-modifying treatments for any form of neurodegeneration with brain iron accumulation. Treatment options remain supportive and palliative. Multidisciplinary approach with close collaboration between health care professionals is needed. This includes: Neurologic management of extrapyramidal and pyramidal disorders, seizures, and sleep disturbance; neuropsychiatric symptoms;

There are several promising treatments currently under active investigation These treatments can be grouped under four broad approaches: Iron chelation to treat brain iron deposits; Metabolite supplementation to restore metabolic deficits in CoA pathway Such as Co-A, Cyclic PPA; PANK3 activation; GENE therapy to introduce a functional copy of the PANK2 gene; Gene therapy. Gene therapy would be an attractive option for medically intractable life-limiting NBIA disorders. Deep brain stimulation (DBS) has been undertaken in some patients with NBIA, and mainly in PKAN with intractable dystonia. Overall, it appears that DBS is generally a **safe and well-tolerated procedure** it may be a reasonable option for the palliation of severe pharmaco-resistant dystonia.

Take home message

- A. Early diagnosis in movement disorders with neurodegeneration will improve prognosis and aid in genetic testing of proband and counselling for prevention in progeny.
- B. Spectrum of movement disorders associated with brain iron accumulation labelled as NBIA have received a new limelight with development of better techniques of MR imaging.
- C. Understanding of these disorders have also opened new areas for research in understanding iron metabolism in health and diseases of the CNS.

Better understanding of pathology underlying spectrum of NBIA has paved way for newer treatment approaches.